

RELEASE-AI: A Lifecycle Framework for Artificial Intelligence Development and Disclosure Control in Trusted Research Environments

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Abstract

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) provide secure access to personal and sensitive data, such as Electronic Healthcare Records (EHRs), for approved research. The increasing use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in health research introduces new challenges for managing privacy risks of individuals' data. We present a comprehensive framework that embeds mitigation strategies throughout the entire AI project lifecycle, structured across six project phases: design, governance, development, evaluation, disclosure control, and release.

This framework aims to empower all stakeholders - researchers, project teams, output checkers, and TRE staff - with clear, phase-specific recommendations on which measures and checks are necessary before model release to help identify potential disclosure risks to data. It promotes early identification of risks with corresponding mitigations and ensures responsibilities are clearly assigned to relevant actors at each stage, from initial planning through to deployment and monitoring. Mitigation strategies include good AI/ML practices, both in terms of code and documentation, privacy-enhancing techniques during training and evaluation, restricting model access via secure query systems, licencing agreements, and adversarial attack testing using tools like SACRO-ML. This process highlights the need to train everyone involved appropriately with relevant role-specific material. A novel overall project risk assessment is proposed, categorising AI projects based on the likelihood of attack and associated sensitive data leakage risks. By integrating a lifecycle-focused risk management process with a scalable disclosure control, this approach enables innovative AI research while maintaining rigorous data protection standards and public trust.

Introduction

As the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) becomes increasingly common in research, ensuring responsible and secure handling of sensitive data is essential—particularly within Trusted Research Environments (TREs). AI/ML projects present unique challenges to disclosure control due to their complexity, potential for indirect data leakage, and evolving threat landscape. While existing TRE policies and procedures provide robust frameworks for traditional statistical outputs, they require adaptation and expansion to address the specific risks associated with AI/ML model development and deployment.

This document outlines our proposed process for applying disclosure control measures to AI/ML models training and/or tested within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE). It is intended to guide TRE users, TRE operators, and project teams to help with compliance with information governance and disclosure risk mitigation requirements throughout the life cycle of an AI/ML project in line with best practice recommendations(1–4).

Actors

- *Researcher or TRE user* – The person or persons who analyse and manipulate the raw data given by the TRE provider and who create the model.
- *Project team* – Refers to the team of data analysts and project manager(s) working on a specific project that uses a TRE. Not everyone in the team will be a TRE user necessarily.
- *Output checkers* – Individuals authorised to review outputs for disclosure risk prior to release from the TRE.
- *Data Controller* – person, team or entity who owns, is a custodian or a controller of the sensitive data or acts on behalf of the data owner following their instructions.
- *TRE operator* (sometimes referred as ‘TRE’ in this document)– people employed by the TRE for different processes including governance, infrastructure, data linkage, pseudonymisation, and output checkers.

Box 1. Actors. Definition of broad categories of actors relevant for RELEASE-AI. They are based on SATRE Roles and UK TRE Glossary.

Through the **RELEASE-AI (Risk Evaluation and Lifecycle Accountability for Secure Egress of Artificial Intelligence) framework**, extra steps for AI/ML projects are provided, supplementing the TRE’s Standard Operating Procedures(5–7) for ‘non-AI’ outputs. It is assumed that TRE users will want to egress outputs analysing the performance of their models (e.g., figures, tables), code, and pipelines. Documentation such as papers or internal guides, are highly likely to be written and published. Although these outputs may contain indirect information about the data, they are not considered specific AI risks and, therefore, are outside the scope of this document. This framework assumes researchers and projects are trustworthy, and will not intentionally attempt to egress sensitive data or bypass checks.

RELEASE-AI Framework

The RELEASE-AI framework is designed around six key phases of a project using a TRE, as illustrated in Figure 1:

- (i) Design - where the Project Team develops the overall plan for the project.
- (ii) Governance, which involves discussions between the Project Team and the TRE Operator, approvals are sought, and agreements are signed.
- (iii) Development, where Researchers access the TRE and sensitive data in order to clean and analyse data and develop AI/ML models.
- (iv) Evaluation where the outputs are benchmarked, and self-assessment for disclosure control should be performed.
- (v) Disclosure Control, when the TRE Operator assess potential risks of data breach.
- (vi) Release, when the final model is released out of the TRE.

General considerations, although they are not essential for privacy, are pieces of advice to ensure timely project success for everyone involved. For additional and detailed information on each of the following statements, consult the supplementary information.

Figure 1. Lifecycle of AI project responsibilities. AI/ML projects have six phases. In each phase actions and actors are defined to ensure a successful and smooth model release.

General considerations

- **C1.** TRE Operators and Users need specific training on the additional risks introduced by different types of ML, mitigation strategies, and data privacy for AI/ML in general(1,3,4). The training should be role specific for everyone involved.
- **C2.** Disclosure control for AI/ML models requires specialised tools, processes, and expertise. Output checking for some types of models might not be supported or possible. In other cases, it can be complex and require extra resources(3).
- **C3.** Computational costs to train a model, and subsequently assess the model for disclosure risk, may be high, depending on the method used, the data volume and its dimensionality.
- **C4.** Releasing multiple models within a project, trained using different data splits, parameters or initialisations (excluding those methods that by design combine several models with only one final output to the user, such as ensemble methods), can introduce risks such as disclosure via differencing that must be evaluated(8). The type and number of models to be egressed should be planned, discussed, and agreed between the Project Team and the TRE Operators at the proposal stage.

Each of the following items is marked according to its importance for disclosure control: mandatory [+++], recommended [++], or optional [+]. The main actors responsible for each item are indicated by a corresponding symbol shown alongside the statement.

Design phase

- **DS1.** [+] Experts on the data to be analysed, AI privacy, ethicists, AI developers, and data scientists could be consulted or employed throughout the duration of the project (1,2,9,10).
- **DS2.** [++] The Project Team should contact the TRE provider to help outline the feasibility of the project. The Project Team should consider which AI/ML techniques

are appropriate for the project and supported by the TRE. This should include whether the amount of data available is sufficient for AI/ML.

- **DS3.** [+++] Mitigation measures must be defined, including privacy-enhancing strategies (e.g., Safe Model wrappers, differential privacy(10)), addressing class imbalance, and how to implement best practices to prevent data leakage.
- **DS4.** [+++] The Project Team must specify the number and type of models to be ingressed and egressed (e.g., regression, classification, generative AI) and where the model is proposed to be deployed (such as third-party systems and devices including wearables or third-party secure environments).
- **DS5.** [++] The Project Team should attempt to quantify the expected benefit of the risk score and the expected cost from disclosure risks on a comparable scale. Decisions on data security processes should be made with consideration of this risk-cost-benefit trade-off, with awareness that, in general, actions to improve data security (e.g. differential privacy, model choice restriction) will impair performance and reduce benefit.

Governance phase

- **G1.** [+++] The Project Team is responsible for the model created and outputs generated. They must align as a 'Safe Person' within the Five Safes Framework(11), they must follow best practices to mitigate bias and prevent harm, such as those outlined in the SPIRIT-AI(12), CONSORT-AI(13), FUTURE-AI(1) , ICO(14) and DOME(15) guidelines. The exact application of these guidelines must be agreed upon at the proposal stage.
- **G2.** [+] The TRE Operator could reserve the right to set aside a portion of the project data extract for disclosure risk assessment(16). In such cases, the Project Team and TRE Users must be informed, and the TRE User must provide the code to process the data and run queries to the model with appropriate documentation. This must be agreed upon in advance and applied only when essential, based on the output check required by the project specifications.
- **G3.** [+++] Mitigation strategies must be identified and agreed to avoid data breaches on deployment. Different mitigations may be required by one or more actors throughout the project duration. They must be clearly identified and applied accordingly.
- **G4.** [+++] The Project Team, TRE operator, and Data Controller must agree on a licence for the output model. The TRE can reserve the right to enforce a preferred licence.

Development phase

- **DEV1.** [+++] The TRE User or Project Team must provide all the information required about any AI/ML model to be ingressed, including type, pre-training details, licence of the pre-trained model and data.
- **DEV2.** [++] The TRE Operator should perform an ingress risk assessment for any AI/ML pre-trained models, according to TRE operational procedures for ingress. TRE Operator could recognise the need to facilitate fast and simple ingress of small blocks of computer code.
- **DEV3.** [+++] The TRE User must follow best practices for ML and coding(1,2).
- **DEV4.** [++] The TRE User should document the process followed to create the model. This information will be useful or even required for releasing the model. Some

processing and engineering of the data can lead to privacy threats, like data-induced leakage, preprocessing or data split-related leakage(17).

Evaluation phase

- **E1.** [+] TRE Users could perform benchmarking of the model against the current standards. This (optional) information could be essential in some circumstances for disclosure control to reach a verdict.
- **E2.** [+++] The generated model must comply with all the TRE requirements. The TRE User must provide all agreed documentation and information on how the model was created.
- **E3.** [++] TRE Users should use ‘SACRO-ML’ tool(18),and/or any other tools used by the TRE for disclosure control, for self-evaluation prior to request release.

Disclosure control phase

- **DC1.** [+] Projects could be categorised according to the overall risk of data privacy issues, based on project characteristics, mitigation measures applied, and the likelihood of the model created being attacked. Lower risk projects could have less strict, or even less disclosure controls, whereas high risk projects could need more strict or extra controls, as shown in Table 1. This must be defined by the TRE Operator and communicated with the Project Team.

Table 1 Project Risk categorisation. Projects can be categorised according to different scenarios and the overall risks in terms of potential data breaches. Mitigation measures could be more relaxed for low-risk projects.

Project risk category	Scenarios	Controls
Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No model egress. • Data anonymised either by TRE Operator or Researcher. • Model trained on synthetic data. • Raw data is highly unlikely to be reproduced without prior knowledge. e.g. certain types of medical images. • No personal or sensitive data was included. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance only.
Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Model deployed in a third party trusted and access-controlled environment. • Model is hosted in a TRE operator trusted safe and query-controlled environment and can be queried publicly. • Model released into a third-party environment (non-trusted). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance. • Simulated attacks. • Checks for model specific threats.
High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When the model is deployed in a system that is more vulnerable to attacks than current accepted standards or not safe. • Models that explicitly store data or their output can replicate training data. • When certain output check controls cannot be done, e.g. ‘SACRO-ML’ tools cannot be applied. • The dataset that the model has been trained on has some interest for someone, for example for economic reasons or because it contains celebrity data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must apply mitigations measures and reassess. • Egress only in special circumstances, e.g. the benefit is clearly substantial.

- **DC2.** [+++] The TRE User must provide all the information required for the TRE disclosure control process. This may include: documentation, code, benchmarks, etc.
- **DC3.** [+++] The Output Checkers must perform the AI/ML specific disclosure controls required according to the TRE Standard Operating Procedures, and any other checks as agreed for the specific project.
- **DC4.** [++] Outputs should be evaluated carefully within the overall context, not only individually. Metadata associated with the project (data, model, processing, engineering, etc.) could potentially increase the risk of disclosure. For example, details of the data distribution could lead to an adversarial attacker to be more successful.

Release phase

- **R1.** [+] A register of projects with details of the type of model, dataset and other project specific information could be beneficial to estimate future project risks for the TRE Operator.
- **R2.** [+++] The TRE must provide all the outputs requested and approved for egress in appropriate means for transfer.
- **R3.** [+] The project team could maintain a model use register (either TRE-specific or via subscription to a national service).
- **R4.** [+] A plan for reviewing and potentially decommissioning the model could be encouraged to have. For example, when the model is out of date, not fit for purpose anymore, or issues detected including data privacy related.

Method

RELEASE-AI is a structured framework across six phases of projects within TREs. It aims to provide guidance on the safe egress of ML/AI models focusing on controls, standards and recommendations. The development of this framework began by outlining the broad general process for AI/ML model disclosure control. Six phases for projects were identified, and guidance was collected for each. Experts involved in TREs, including those in governance, data management, infrastructure, and output checkers, were consulted. Input from AI/ML experts and users were also incorporated.

The collected guidance was then arranged according to the defined project phases and consolidated into a set of general statements within each project phase. Overall general considerations were included to be acknowledged for all the stakeholders involved in AI/ML projects in TREs. To the greatest extent possible, duplication with existing published guidance was avoided.

The statements were coded according to the phase (DS for DeSign, G for Governance, DEV for Development, E for Evaluation, DC for Disclosure Control, and R for Release) and general considerations (C for considerations), followed by a number. Each statement includes the main actor responsible for the implementation, identified by a symbol. The actors are defined in Box 1, based on the UK TRE community definitions [<https://glossary.uktre.org/en/latest/>] and adapted for this framework. The statements are classified from mandatory, symbolised with [+++], when they are critical for the safe release of the model; recommended, symbolised with [++], when it may enhance privacy protection in many cases, although not essential assuming other measures are in place; to optional, symbolised with [+], for those measures that are not essential, however in some circumstances could be useful or even necessary.

RELEASE-AI was designed to facilitate faster, smoother, and safe egress of models from TREs, while enabling public benefit research. It should be applied alongside the relevant guidance and legal framework. To maintain the framework's usability and readability, detailed information has been provided in the supplementary material.

Discussion

The widespread adoption of AI and ML techniques for analysing sensitive data is now a well-established reality. Previous initiatives, including GRAIMATTER(3), SACRO(19), and the SDC-Reboot community, highlighted the need for tailored guidance designed specifically TREs supporting AI/ML research projects. These efforts emphasise the importance of clearly defining which risks may emerge, establishing systematic

approaches for risk assessment, identifying appropriate controls and preventative measures, and allocating responsibilities to relevant stakeholders.

Three principal risk domains have emerged in the literature on privacy-preserving AI/ML models. The first involves data leakage risks(5–7), which often arise from vulnerabilities in data collection, e.g. bias, and preprocessing pipelines—such as class imbalance—that may increase the likelihood of inadvertent disclosure(5,7,8). While techniques like differential privacy can mitigate such risks, they often come at the expense of model performance(9). The second domain relates to AI/ML methodological risks. Not all types can be applied to every task(9). Instance-based models such as Support Vector Machines (SVMs), embed training data within the model itself. If released outside of a TRE, such models may constitute a data breach(1,9,10,20). Also, appropriate combination of hyperparameters can help reducing risks(14). The third area involves adversarial attacks(1,12–14), where malicious usage of the model can lead to the unintended leakage of sensitive data.

Several domain-specific guidelines have emerged to support privacy-preserving in AI/ML, particularly in sensitive fields such as biomedical research and healthcare(9,12,13,15,21–23). While some frameworks focus on technical implementation, others aim to bridge the gap between regulatory compliance and practical guidance for researchers.

Effective governance includes robust and well-curated processes for data pipelines, secure system access, and comprehensive oversight of both model training and deployment stages(4). Ensuring that such systems comply with data protection regulations and ethical standards is central to mitigating the risks inherent in working with sensitive information.

The DOME recommendations(15), developed through a collaborative community effort, provides technical guidance for conducting AI/ML projects on biological data. It identifies four broad areas where risks of data leakage could emerge, offering guidance for each. Complementing this, Bennett *et al*(9) distils these concerns into seven guiding questions, covering issues such as data bias, inter-sample similarities, and missing features. While DOME is primarily intended for technical audience, Bennett’s questions are designed for a broader stakeholder engagement.

In the healthcare domain, the FUTURE-AI guidelines(1) provide a comprehensive framework for conducting responsible AI research. Based on a set of core principles, it offers detailed recommendations addressing critical aspects such as transparency, traceability, usability and robustness as well as broader societal issues such as ethics and the environment. Importantly, FUTURE-AI emphasises the implantation of mitigation measures not only to preserve data privacy, but also to ensure that AI/ML systems perform reliably in real-world settings without introducing harmful biases or unintended consequences.

Notably, some of the recommendations made by this framework align with established legal and regulatory standards for working with sensitive data. However, their direct applicability within TREs may vary, due to the unique operational and governance structures that TREs entail.

TREs are secure platforms designed to enable access to personal and sensitive types of data. They adhere to the Five Safes principles(20), and are subject to strict legal and regulatory requirements. FUTURE-AI covers some of those requirements. Although many TREs typically host healthcare data, many other kinds of sensitive data, such as administrative or tax-related, can be widely accessed too.

Recent work on the privacy issues related to sensitive data emphasises the importance identifying all potential risks, and determine mitigation strategies and regulatory compliance(17). Crucially, these measures should be implemented throughout the entire lifecycle of the model(1,2). However, lifecycle within TREs diverges from general AI/ML practices. TREs provides secure data access, and generally do not collect data. A typical project in a TRE starts with the design, governance, development, evaluation, disclosure control, and release of the model.

TREs require rigorous governance processes to be in place before any project can begin. This includes formal approval procedures, access controls, and role-based permissions. Furthermore, TREs incorporate disclosure control checks at the output stage to ensure that anything leaving the environment do not contain identifiable information. These mechanisms are designed to prevent data leakage and ensure compliance with privacy regulations.

The GRAIMATTER project(3) was the first to explicitly address these challenges, focusing on AI/ML-specific disclosure control within TREs. Its recommendations span technical, legal, ethical, and cost considerations. However, GRAIMATTER primarily addresses only the disclosure control phase, and thus does not cover the full lifecycle of AI/ML model development within TREs.

While those frameworks provide valuable principles for assessing, evaluating and mitigating AI/ML privacy risks, they lack of tailored guidance to the operational constraints of TREs. Notably, these frameworks do not sufficiently address the complexities arising from TRE-specific governance models, and the breadth of AI/ML projects that may be undertaken within such environments. Guidance to support AI/ML projects in TREs must accommodate a wide range of technical, ethical, and legal considerations. Importantly, none of them tackle accountability, which is key to for successful AI/ML projects(4).

To address those gaps, RELEASE-AI proposes a more comprehensive framework for managing AI/ML research in TREs, with a particular emphasis on accountability. Accountability has long been a challenge in AI/ML development, especially in collaborative or multi-actor environments. RELEASE-AI identifies five main categories of stakeholders, each with distinct responsibilities critical to the success of privacy-preserving AI/ML research. Its 28 core recommendations span the entire AI/ML project lifecycle in TREs, offering generalisable yet practical guidance applicable across diverse research settings.

RELEASE-AI emphasises that successful implementation depends not only on technical compliance but also on collaborative governance, role clarity, and the integration of oversight mechanisms throughout the project. In doing so, it seeks to promote both transparency and efficiency while achieving the highest standards of privacy protection.

Conclusions

RELEASE-AI is the first framework specifically designed for AI/ML projects in TREs. It addresses gaps in existing guidance by providing comprehensive, adaptable, and extensible guidance. The framework provides stakeholders clear recommendations to ensure compliant and successful AI/ML projects, identifying potential issues and outlining strategies to address them, thereby facilitating informed decision-making and promoting good AI/ML practices.

The full lifecycle of an AI/ML project with sensitive data in a TRE is considered. RELEASE-AI highlights that success depends on many actions and decisions throughout the 6 phases of the project lifecycle.

By promoting early identification of potential risks and corresponding mitigation strategies, RELEASE-AI enables a structured approach that enhances project efficiency and improves outcomes for all stakeholders involved. Lastly, roles and responsibilities are assigned throughout the project. This role-based approach promotes clarity, transparency, and collaboration. By clearly delineating who is responsible for what and when, RELEASE-AI reduces ambiguity, supports compliance with regulatory requirements, and fosters a culture of shared responsibility.

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References

1. Lekadir K, Feragen A, Fofanah AJ, Frangi AF, Buyx A, Emelie A, et al. FUTURE-AI: International consensus guideline for trustworthy and deployable artificial intelligence in healthcare. *BMJ Open* [Internet]. 2025 Aug 11;388(e081554). Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2309.12325>
2. Shahriar S, Allana S, Hazratifard SM, Dara R. A Survey of Privacy Risks and Mitigation Strategies in the Artificial Intelligence Life Cycle. *IEEE Access*. 2023;11:61829–54.
3. Jefferson E, Liley J, Malone M, Reel S, Crespi-Boixader A, Kerasidou X, et al. GRAIMATTER Green Paper: Recommendations for disclosure control of trained Machine Learning (ML) models from Trusted Research Environments (TREs). *Zenodo* [Internet]. 2022; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/7089491>
4. Papagiannidis E, Mikalef P, Conboy K. Responsible artificial intelligence governance: A review and research framework. *Journal of Strategic Information Systems* [Internet]. 2025;34(2):101885. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsis.2024.101885>
5. Green E, Ritche F, White P. The statbarn: A New Model for Output Statistical Disclosure Control. In: Domingo-Ferrer J, Önen M, editors. *Privacy in Statistical Databases*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland; 2024. p. 284–93.
6. Griffiths E, Greci C, Kotrotsios Y, Parker S, Scott J, Welpton R, et al. Handbook on Statistical Disclosure Control for Outputs [Internet]. 2024. 1–100 p. Available from: <https://securedatagroup.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/sdc-handbook-v2.0.pdf>
7. Alves K, Ritchie F. Runners, repeaters, strangers and aliens: operationalising efficient output disclosure control. *Statistical Journal of the IAOS*. 2020;36(1281).
8. Jagielski M, Wu S, Oprea A, Ullman J, Geambasu R. How to Combine Membership-Inference Attacks on Multiple Updated Machine Learning Models. Vol. 2023, *Proceedings of Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies*. Association for Computing Machinery; 2023. 211–232 p.

9. Bennett J, Blumenthal DB, Grimm DG, Haselbeck F, Joeres R, Kalinina O V., et al. Guiding questions to avoid data leakage in biological machine learning applications. *Nat Methods*. 2024 Aug 1;21(8):1444–53.
10. Hotchkiss L, Squires E, Adeoye K, Sarabandi A, Heys S, Golightly E, et al. Perspectives & Recommendations on the Development of Safe AI in Sensitive Healthcare Data.
11. Ritchie F. The ‘Five Safes’: a framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Zenodo. 2017;
12. Cruz Rivera S, Liu X, Chan AW, Denniston AK, Calvert MJ, Darzi A, et al. Guidelines for clinical trial protocols for interventions involving artificial intelligence: the SPIRIT-AI extension. *Nat Med*. 2020;26(9):1351–63.
13. Liu X, Cruz Rivera S, Moher D, Calvert M, Denniston AK, Spirit-ai T, et al. CONSORT-AI extension. *Nat Med*. 2020;26(September):1364–74.
14. ICO (Information Commissioner’s Office). AI and data protection risk toolkit [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2025 Sep 1]. Available from: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/artificial-intelligence/guidance-on-ai-and-data-protection/ai-and-data-protection-risk-toolkit/>
15. Walsh I, Fishman D, Garcia-Gasulla D, Titma T, Pollastri G, Capriotti E, et al. DOME: recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology. *Nat Methods*. 2021;18(10):1122–7.
16. Black JE, Kueper JK, Williamson TS. An introduction to machine learning for classification and prediction. *Fam Pract*. 2023 Feb 1;40(1):200–4.
17. Apicella A, Isgrò F, Prevete R. Don’t Push the Button! Exploring Data Leakage Risks in Machine Learning and Transfer Learning. 2024 Jan 24; Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2401.13796>
18. Smith J, Preen RJ, McCarthy A, Albashir M, Crespi-Boixader A, Mumtaz S, et al. Safe machine learning model release from Trusted Research Environments: The SACRO-ML package. 2022 Dec 2; Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2212.01233>
19. J.E. Smith, M. Albashir, S. Bacon, B. Butler-Cole, J. Caldwell, C. Cole, A. Crespi Boixander, E. Green, E. Jefferson, Y. Jones, S. Krueger, J. Liley, A. McNeill, K. O’Sullivan, K. Oldfield, R. Preen, F. Ritchie, L. Robinson, S. Rogers, P. Stokes, A. Tilbr PW. Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs (SACRO). Zenodo [Internet]. 2023; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/10055365>
20. Ritchie F. The ‘Five Safes’: a framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Zenodo [Internet]. 2017; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/record/897821>
21. An Q, Rahman S, Zhou J, Kang JJ. A Comprehensive Review on Machine Learning in Healthcare Industry: Classification, Restrictions, Opportunities and Challenges. *Sensors*. 2023;23(9).
22. Messeri L, Crockett MJ. Artificial intelligence and illusions of understanding in scientific research. *Nature*. 2024;627(8002):49–58.
23. Stock A, Gregr EJ, Chan KMA. Data leakage jeopardizes ecological applications of machine learning. Vol. 7, *Nature Ecology and Evolution*. *Nature Research*; 2023. p. 1743–5.